

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D7.3 Final report on dissemination, outreach, engagement and exploitation and on IPSP Global Network Platform

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Consortium Overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGEN STIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR

JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Acronyms

CAP	Common Access Point
DCC	Diamond Capacity Center
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
ED & I	Equity, Diversity & Inclusion
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standards for Institutional Publishing
ERA	European Research Area
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
IPTP	Institutional Publishing Technology Provider
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
NCC	National Capacity Center
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
RF / RFO	Research Funder / Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
TF	Task Force
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Work Package 7 (WP7) facilitated communication and dissemination of the work, results and outputs of the DIAMAS project. It focused its activities on targeted stakeholders and engaged their communities throughout the project. The actions to secure the exploitation and sustainability of the DIAMAS results and outputs were designed and put in place.

Objectives

WP7 undertook a wide range of actions, all closely aligned with the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) set out in the project proposal. The work package aimed to:

- 1) create a solid, recognisable brand identity for DIAMAS
- 2) develop and deploy the strategies for dissemination, engagement, exploitation, and outreach
- 3) assist in the recruitment of stakeholders participating in project activities by providing input and validation
- 4) promote the project's activities and outputs, engage with different stakeholder groups to co-create, validate, and discuss project outcomes
- 5) deploy activities aimed at widening and maximising impact in the European Research Area (ERA) and beyond; and
- 6) ensure uptake and sustainability of the project's key exploitable results (KER)

The final report on Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation and on the IPSP Global Network Platform (D7.3) describes the achievements of Work Package 7 of the DIAMAS project.

Dissemination and Outreach

During the project a comprehensive set of tools, resources and guidelines were developed to support the quality and sustainability of Diamond Open Access publishing, with the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) as a core resource. To aid the implementation of DOAS, DIAMAS has created a Toolsuite, the DOAS Self-Assessment tool and several Guidelines. Additional materials included financial sustainability resources and the Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) Getting Started Guide. All resources are presented on the EDCH Training Platform, a modular training programme released in May 2025.

DIAMAS's outreach efforts included the use of different communication channels. Besides the website DIAMAS created content for several social media platforms – Twitter/X, LinkedIn and YouTube – to inform the wider community about progress and results of the project. Additionally, it used newsletters, blog posts and non-peer-reviewed publications and press releases to share more in-depth information about specific items and topics related to the project. Finally, 7 campaigns were designed to launch and highlight important project results and outputs, and to draw attention to key developments such as the launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) in January 2025.

The DIAMAS website proved to be a vital instrument and functioned as the central hub for all knowledge, information and results from the project.

Engagement

The work package focused on engaging and activating 9 main stakeholder communities: Funders, IPSPs, Learned societies, Libraries, OA Diamond Action Plan signatories, Policymakers, RPOs, Research assessment agencies and Researchers, teachers and students. Fundamental to these efforts is the stakeholder database holding over 1,100 entries across the 9 stakeholder groups. More than 60 DIAMAS organised events ensured the participation of over 4,000 experts, with an average of 60 participants per event. DIAMAS partners actively participated in an impressive 109 third-party events, presenting the results and outputs of the project.

All the engagement activities secured the building and maintenance of a large and engaged diamond open access community. A significant milestone was the DIAMAS Final Conference held in June 2025, bringing together over 320 registered participants.

Exploitation

The objectives of the exploitation plan drafted in month 6 of the DIAMAS project aimed to provide support to a future network of Diamond Capacity Centres (DCC) as well as to create the building blocks of the EDCH federated infrastructure to help journals align with quality standards and guidelines.

To meet the objectives of the exploitation plan DIAMAS resources were uploaded into Zenodo and the EDCH and were additionally made openly under a CC BY licence to allow their reuse and adaptation. DIAMAS Tools were as much as possible developed with open-source software and delivered as open-ended interoperable components. To engage an audience as wide as possible, the DOAS Self-Assessment Tool was translated into multiple languages.

Project partners will contribute to the long-term sustainability and further development of the project's tools through partners' in-kind contributions.

Maximising and widening impact

DIAMAS deployed activities aimed at widening and maximising impact in the ERA and beyond to ensure the uptake and sustainability of the project's KERs. To achieve this, DIAMAS engaged with national networks and initiatives, associations of university presses and library consortia, and regional and international networks identified in the stakeholder database.

Factsheets were created and blog posts were published to promote key outputs and engage specific stakeholders. Several outputs were transformed into practical resources such as the detailed report on IPSP best practices. The team published conference presentations and organised in-person and online presentations and workshops for publishers and editors to enable the dissemination and uptake of DIAMAS outputs beyond the partner countries and encouraged discussion in multiple languages.

IPSP Global Network Platform

A dedicated Task (T7.5) worked on the exploitation and sustainability of the IPSP global network within the DIAMAS project. This included creating a thriving Diamond Open Access community that would last beyond the project's lifespan and would serve as a stepping stone for further development and scalability on a global level. To facilitate this transition, the DIAMAS online Common Access Point was developed together with focused efforts to motivate the community to transfer from DIAMAS to the EDCH.

After the launch of the EDCH, communication efforts focussed on transferring the DIAMAS community to the EDCH, securing the further uptake and sustainability of the DIAMAS outputs beyond the project's end date. The actions to further secure the uptake and development of DIAMAS resources beyond the project are presented in the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan.

Conclusions and further steps

While WP7 led the delivery of communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation activities, the successful results reflect the significant contributions of all consortium partners.

The results of WP7 by far exceeded the expectations set in the planning phase. All objectives as described in Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) are successfully met.

Developments in the field of Diamond Open Access publishing have taken a significant leap forward since the drafting of the project proposal for DIAMAS. Although many initiatives around Diamond Open Access took place at the same time, the actions and activities of DIAMAS, widely communicated and disseminated through this work

package, and led by a dedicated and inspiring team of project partners as well as an engaged European and global Diamond OA community, certainly contributed to the changes in the landscape.

The future uptake of the DIAMAS legacy was secured by laying the groundwork through consistent community engagement and by building a new, longer-term home for DIAMAS, the EDCH. The further evolution of DIAMAS results already began during the project when the Common Access Point evolved into the European Diamond Capacity Hub.

In 2025, the opportunity was taken to scale DIAMAS outputs globally in the ALMASI project, with both projects sharing the same lead organisation. The vast community of practice that has been formed and facilitated by the EDCH Registry and Forum provides a steady foundation for the further uptake of DIAMAS outputs.

1. Introduction

1.1 Overview and Aims

This document outlines the results regarding dissemination, outreach, engagement, and exploitation throughout the DIAMAS project. By following the strategies and proposals described in D7.2 'Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation Plan', the project has built an active and engaged community, ensuring that the efforts of DIAMAS reached their intended audiences and have the intended impact. Stakeholders were engaged throughout.. Moreover, this final report focuses on the exploitation and sustainability of the results beyond the DIAMAS project's lifetime.

Results are reported against the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and structured around the Key Exploitable Results (KERs), identified in the project proposal. They align closely with the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR), which was also set out in the project proposal.

The actions set out in the PEDR aimed to:

- 1) create a solid, recognisable brand identity for DIAMAS;
- 2) develop and deploy the strategies for dissemination, engagement, exploitation, and outreach;
- 3) assist in the recruitment of stakeholders participating in project activities by producing input and validation;
- 4) promote the project's activities and outputs, engage with different stakeholder groups to co-create, validate, and discuss project outcomes;
- 5) deploy activities aiming at widening and maximising impact in the European Research Area (ERA) and beyond; and
- 6) ensure uptake and sustainability of the project's key exploitable results (KER).

This document is closely linked to the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) and uses it as a starting point; its contents have been significantly adapted to set out a clear pathway to achieve DIAMAS's goals, with concrete proposals and tailored actions. Throughout the project, the methods, tools and timeframes for achieving DIAMAS's goals were adjusted and refined to support project delivery.

While Work Package 7 (WP7) led the delivery of communication, dissemination, engagement and exploitation activities, the successful results reflect the significant contributions of all consortium partners.

1.2 Structure of the report

The following section describes the results of the dissemination, outreach and engagement strategies presented earlier in the project (D7.2). It then examines the exploitation and sustainability of DIAMAS results beyond the project's lifetime, as well as the further development of the IPSP Global Network Platform, including its transformation into the European Diamond Capacity Hub. The exploitation and sustainability plan presents a more actionable approach. The report concludes by outlining the next steps.

2. Dissemination and Outreach

In December 2023, a dissemination, outreach, engagement, and exploitation plan (D7.2) was completed and subsequently maintained to support strategic communication planning and coordination for the remainder of the project. A rolling KPI tracker monitored the effectiveness of the communication activities, including web traffic, social media engagement, event participation, and reuse of project materials.

At the start of the project, thirteen communications staff members from partner organisations were identified. They supported dissemination and outreach activities throughout the project. In addition to DIAMAS's communication channels, partners also used their own channels, contributing to effective dissemination of project results across all targeted stakeholder groups. Close collaboration with WP4 and WP5 supported dissemination of the Toolsuite, Guidelines, and engagement outputs.

During the project, comprehensive dissemination and outreach activities promoted DIAMAS's objectives, deliverables, and tools to a wide range of stakeholders. The activities focused particularly on Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs), funders, policymakers, researchers, and open access advocates, as well as learned societies. Activities such as collaborative research and webinars ran throughout the project. These activities used a multi-channel, multilingual approach to ensure high visibility, engagement and uptake across the European Research Area and beyond.

2.1 Replacing IPSP with Diamond

After discussions about the term IPSP, which was often perceived as jargon, the DIAMAS consortium agreed to use Diamond (Diamond Open Access) as the primary term and to gradually replace IPSP in external communications. To support this change, two actions were taken: first, internal communication guidelines were issued to instruct all consortium members on preferred terminology and phrasing across the project; second, the project website was subsequently rewritten to reflect the new use of Diamond.

2.2 Towards the European Diamond Open Access Hub (EDCH)

Towards the end of the project, dissemination and outreach focused on informing and engaging the wider community, and on fostering uptake of project results such as publications, tools, training materials, as well as guidelines and recommendations. With the launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub in January 2025, communication and dissemination activities focussed on highlighting the EDCH as both a federated infrastructure and a collective supporting the community of practice around Diamond OA.

2.3 Key Exploitable Results

The DIAMAS project aimed to deliver multiple Key Exploitable Results to enhance understanding of the current state of institutional scholarly publishing in Europe. Identifying target users was crucial for the successful exploitation of the project’s results. Dissemination and engagement activities paved the way for exploitation by building a strong stakeholder network and sustaining engagement within the DIAMAS community. All nine identified stakeholder groups were also targets for exploitation activities, given that they are the most interested in and will benefit from the project results.

KERs as stated in project proposal

Key Exploitable Results	Target Stakeholder	Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy
Landscape mapping & gap analysis	All stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement throughout project and consortium comms channels - Early release of data under CCO - Dissemination and preservation on Zenodo under CCO - Continuous communication through global network platform
DOAS (formerly known as EQSIP)	IPSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through project events (webinars and workshops) - Dissemination and preservation on Zenodo under CCO - Continuous communication through Global Network platform - Regular Updates with engagement via Global Network forum
Global Network, including EDCH, Common Access Point (CAP), toolsuite, training materials, guidelines and forum	IPSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination through project and consortium communication channels - Integration in OPERAS catalogue of services for continuous communication and support
ED&I Tools	IPSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through events (webinars and workshop) - Engagement and dissemination through project and consortium communication channels - Outreach via T7.4 - Integration in the global network platform supported by OPERAS - Outreach via the international advisory board

Quality and sustainability self-assessment tools	IPSP and institutions' financial departures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through project events (webinars and workshop) - Continuous communication through Global Network platform - Technical sustainability of the Self Assessment Tools ensured by FECYT
Actionable recommendations	RFOs, RPOs, policy-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through project events (webinars and workshop) - Continuous communication through Global Network platform - Continuous advocacy and updates by specialised umbrella organisations: EUA (RPOs), Science Europe (RFO), OPERAS (national policy-making bodies)
All KERs	All stakeholders	ALL KERs will be integrated in the 'Institutional Publishing Global Network' that will become one of the core services of OPERAS

Key project outputs were systematically published on [Zenodo](#), with appropriate metadata and licensing to facilitate reuse. Dissemination was complemented by visual storytelling (e.g. infographics, speaker profiles) and by amplification through the institutional channels of consortium partners. These outputs were linked to the Common Access Point and, subsequently, to the European Diamond Capacity Hub. Related resources were mapped to workflows and tools that IPSPs across Europe can use to meet current quality and operational standards. Furthermore, the outputs are openly available under a CC BY 4.0 licence, which allows reuse and adaptation (e.g., translation) in the Diamond Capacity Centres managed by project partners, as well as by new centres.

All major communications were branded in line with the DIAMAS visual identity, with a transition to the European Diamond Capacity Hub branding during the project's final phase to support sustainability and continuity beyond the project's lifetime.

2.4 Dissemination and Outreach: achievements

DIAMAS's dissemination and outreach activities aimed to fulfil key aims outlined in the PEDR, including establishing a solid and recognisable brand for DIAMAS, recruiting stakeholders for future activities, and promoting the project's activities and outputs. To achieve this, DIAMAS shared information about events, project developments and results, and related news, using the project website, social media channels, newsletters, publications, and printed materials, where appropriate. A set of campaigns was rolled out, using the communication tools to raise awareness and share information. Throughout all these activities, the project used a set of messages to convey the project's meaning and importance, aims, and activities.

The results of the dissemination and outreach actions far exceeded the expectations set at the start of the project, contributing to the success of the project. What stands out in particular is the large audiences that were reached via the different communication channels, such as social media followers and newsletter contacts. Also, the large number of new visitors to the website, almost 5 times the target, shows the high interest in the project.

The table below gives an overview of the initial targets and actual results of DIAMAS outreach and dissemination activities at the end of the project.

Area	Description	Time frame	Target	Target end of project	Actuals August 2025
Social Media	Tweets (including retweets)	Per Year	800	2,400	2490
	Twitter followers (outside project)	Project	500	500	1,162 Total followers
	LinkedIn posts	Per Year	40	120	133
	LinkedIn Followers	Project	100	100	799
	YouTube		-	-	15
Communication materials	Newsletters	Per Year	3	9	13 emails 2041 contacts
	Blog posts and non-peer-reviewed publications	Per Year	10	30	15 (External) 40 (DIAMAS site) TOTAL: 55
	Press releases	Project	3	3	1
Campaigns	Campaign	Project	3	3	7 in total: - Survey-a-thon - Open Access Week 23 Interviews - Landscape report results - DOAS/DOASATHON - Diamond open access recommendation guidelines - Sustainability Toolsuite - European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)
Website	Unique visitors (users)	Per Month	300	10,800	Total number new users August 2025: 49.107 Average new users per month based on 36 months: 1.364 Recurring users based on 36 months: 7.085
Publications	Scientific publications	Project	8		8
Training materials	An online educational programme	Project	1		1
	Institutional sustainability	Project	1		1

	self-assessment tool				
Guidelines and recommendations	A guidebook that aggregates existing guidelines and can create new ones as needed	Project	1		1
	Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines (for institutions, FSD's, policymakers)	Project	3		3
	A suite of resources to support the growth of IPSP sustainability	Project	1		1

The following sections give insight into what has been achieved with regard to the use of social media, communication materials, campaigns, website, publications, training materials, as well as guidelines and recommendations.

2.4.1 Social media

DIAMAS employed a social media strategy across three platforms to help raise awareness and build the project's audience: Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. These communication channels were intended to target specific stakeholder groups and to reach a wider audience. Utilising these means of communication helped raise awareness of project results, while Zenodo stored the full results.

The uptake of social media presence for both channels exceeded expectations in the number of posts and the number of followers. A steady increase was seen throughout the project in the number of tweets as well as LinkedIn posts, growing to over 2600 posts and reposts (the latter only available for Twitter/X) in total over 3 years. Project partners also used Facebook and Bluesky to (re)post DIAMAS outputs.

During the project, changes to the ownership of Twitter (later X) in autumn of 2022 led to numerous updates to the platform and to some users migrating away from the service. The situation with X and the impact on the strategic dissemination of DIAMAS was carefully monitored. Since LinkedIn seemed to be taking over from those followers who left X, no additional social media channel was set up before the end of the project.

2.4.2 Communication materials

DIAMAS regularly published a dedicated newsletter, sharing project updates and broader information about OA, using content from the DIAMAS website and external sources featuring DIAMAS. The newsletter was a key tool for communicating, helping to establish an audience and building a community around the project. Community members interested in following project updates could sign up via a link on the DIAMAS website homepage. Over the course of the project, DIAMAS aimed to publish a minimum of nine newsletters. Additionally, 15 project partners who had their own newsletters

were encouraged to share DIAMAS updates at appropriate moments, and consequently, news items were pushed to relevant external newsletters.

During the project, DIAMAS sent a total of 13 newsletters by email to 2041 contacts, 3 during the first year and 5 in both years 2 and 3. This exceeded the 9 newsletters that were promised during the project's lifetime.

In total, 55 blog posts and non-peer-reviewed publications were posted, 40 of which were published via the DIAMAS website, and 15 via external channels.

The number of press releases was slightly lower than proposed. The reason for this is that it was noticed that most journalists were already informed through social media and the DIAMAS website. It was therefore decided that more effort was given to blogs and non-peer-reviewed publications rather than press publications.

2.4.3 Campaigns

In the initial communication and dissemination plan, at least three coordinated campaigns were proposed to help draw attention to the project. Each campaign would have a theme or concept, with associated branding and messages. Events, blogs, news pieces, and other materials accompanied each campaign.

During the project's lifecycle, 7 high-impact dissemination campaigns were designed around major project outputs such as the [Institutional Publishing Landscape Survey Report](#), the [Diamond Open Access Standard \(DOAS\)](#), the [International Recommendations and Guidelines for Open Access](#), the [Sustainability Toolsuite](#) and the [European Diamond Capacity Hub](#).

Campaigns included:

- Production of blogs and regular updates on the DIAMAS website
- Social media posts on LinkedIn and X (Twitter), coordinated with EDCH channels.
- Dedicated newsletters
- Press releases shared via partner networks.

Furthermore, promotional materials, including the printed DOAS booklet and visual graphics for conferences and webinars, were created and disseminated to interested parties.

2.4.4 Website

The project website acted as a central information point for DIAMAS, presenting the project, its aims, composition, and results. The news section of the website proved to be a key channel for communicating outputs, upcoming events, event summaries, and project updates. Longer news items were created as pages that could be shared via DIAMAS social media channels and the newsletter, directing attention to the website and contributing to our website views KPI.

Members of the consortium wrote content for the website to ensure different partners' voices are heard, their work is shared, and the project communications reflect all participants. Website content was created in coordination with WP7, supporting the development of stories and news, editing, providing guidance and feedback, images, and uploading to the website. For project results, the website has a dedicated page to log all [outputs](#), linking to the Zenodo repository.

The DIAMAS website indeed proved to be a central platform and channel for the DIAMAS community. While a total of 10,800 unique visitors were expected towards the end of the project, this number was more than 4 times higher and exceeded a total of more than 49,000 unique visitors.

The DIAMAS website's importance is recognised, and it will remain accessible by being added in the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine after the final review at the end of 2025.

2.4.5 Publications

To share information about the project and reach a broader audience, DIAMAS shared its results and findings through both scientific and non-scientific publications, such as specialised magazines and blogs. WP7 primarily focused on non-scientific publications. However, a total of 8 scientific (peer-reviewed) publications were published during the project, including 6 journal articles, one book chapter and one other publication. These were shared and promoted through the communication activities discussed in this document.

2.4.6 Tools, Guidelines and Training materials

The DIAMAS project has developed a comprehensive set of resources and guidelines to support the quality and sustainability of Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing. It includes a variety of resources specifically tailored to meet the needs of Diamond OA publishers, journal editors and service providers. This presentation will highlight the key components of the knowledge base, with a special focus on the training platform.

At the core of the resources is the [Diamond Open Access Standard \(DOAS\)](#) – a quality framework that sets out required and desired criteria across seven key components of

scholarly publishing: (1) Funding; (2) Legal ownership, mission and governance; (3) Open Science; (4) Editorial management, editorial quality, and research integrity; (5) Technical service efficiency; (6) Visibility, communication, marketing, and impact; and (7) Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB), multilingualism, and gender equity (Consortium of the DIAMAS project 2024).

To aid the implementation of this core framework, DIAMAS has created:

- [Toolsuite](#): A series of short, high-level articles introducing the core components of DOAS, complemented by glossaries, keywords, and frequently asked questions (FAQ), all of which are available in English, Spanish, Croatian, and Portuguese (Armengou, Alevizos, et al. 2024).
- [DOAS Self-Assessment tool](#): In addition to the Diamond Open Access Standard itself, the Self-Assessment tool provides an intuitive user experience for Diamond OA publishers and Diamond OA service providers to analyse their level of compliance with the DOAS and sustainability parameters. The Self-Assessment tool was translated into multiple languages (Rico-Castro, de Pablo Llorente, 2024).
- [Guidelines](#): A collection of 18 articles providing practical advice for aligning publishing practices with DOAS criteria. The high-level topics of DOAS are broken down into subtopics that highlight areas where practical guidance is most needed, e.g. Open Science is addressed through the articles Use of open licenses in open access publishing, Self-archiving policy, Availability of research protocols, methods and software, Handling negative research results, Preprints, and Research data sharing policy. Guidelines are available in English, Spanish, Croatian, and Portuguese (Armengou, Bowker, et al. 2024).

Recognising complexity in certain areas, additional materials were developed:

- [Financial sustainability resources](#): A comprehensive set of resources providing both strategic insights and practical guidance to support the sustainability of Diamond OA publishing. The materials focus on funding models, workforce sustainability, advocacy, and collaborative practices and include guides, templates, case studies, and research (Hughes 2025).
- [Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging \(EDIB\) Getting Started Guide](#), which outlines the core elements of EDIB and offers foundational tools to help editors and publishers create a strategy tailored to their specific context (Bowker, Laakso, and Pölönen 2025).

These resources served as a starting point for developing interactive training materials that address skill gaps identified during the project: the [EDCH Training Platform](#). This is a modular training programme, which was released in late May 2025. It comprises 13 courses hosted on a dedicated Moodle platform within the European Diamond Capacity Hub.

Designed for self-paced learning, it employs diverse formats, including presentations, infographics, checklists, as well as incorporates interactive elements such as quizzes, self-reflection exercises, and flip cards. Training materials can be used as standalone resources or integrated into institutional training efforts. They are released under an open licence and designed for easy localisation and reuse.

The primary audience for the training programme includes journal editors and Diamond OA publishers. However, the materials may also be helpful for trainers, institutional leaders, policymakers, funders, and researchers involved in scholarly communication.

The DIAMAS knowledge base reflects the values of the Diamond OA community: collaboration, openness, and commitment to equitable scholarly communication. By providing standards, tools and training materials, the DIAMAS project supports publishers and service providers in enhancing quality and building more sustainable publishing practices.

To enable further exploitation, the DIAMAS Tools were, as much as possible, developed with open-source software and delivered as open-ended, interoperable components. This approach enables their integration into larger infrastructures and the design of interoperability workflows, allowing the exchange of resources and information across them and enabling the broader community to build upon them in the years to come.

3. Engagement

Engagement during the DIAMAS project focused on engaging and activating all key DIAMAS stakeholder communities - Funders, IPSPs, Learned societies, Libraries, OA Diamond Action Plan signatories, Policymakers, RPOs, Research assessment agencies and Researchers, teachers and students throughout the project lifetime: from 1 September 2023 to 31 August 2025. This engagement task was led by SPARC Europe.

Strategic communication with stakeholders was central to making progress with Diamond OA in Europe. We focused on deepening stakeholder understanding and participation, co-creating and piloting standards, policies, tools and services, to better ensure the adoption of DIAMAS outputs and, above all, helping to create a European Diamond OA community. Recommendations and services were designed to be both ambitious and realistic, grounded in a deep understanding of the needs of institutional publishers. Key outcomes—such as the DIAMAS recommendations, the DOAS quality standard, sustainability services, the EDCH registry, and the EDCH forum—have been

enriched through broad-based community input and collaboration, and we hope that this will lead to greater adoption in the medium term.

3.1 Engagement: achievements

Channel	Activity	Target Groups	Time frame	Target	Participants	KPI Achievement August 2025
Events organised by project	Workshops/webinars organised for engagement, training and outreach purposes	IPSP, RPO, RFOs, Libraries, OA university presses Scholarly societies Relevant initiatives&projects	Project	>54 (online)	>25	63 Events 61 participants (average attendance)
Conferences organised by the project	Conference organised by the project for the promotion of the project's outputs	RPOs, RFOs, Libraries, OA university presses, Scholarly societies, Relevant initiatives &projects, Citizens/General Public	Project	1	>300	1 conference with 103 in-person and 219 online registrations. Total of 322
Participation in third-party events	Participation with presentations in third-party events	RPOs, RFOs, Libraries, OA university presses, Scholarly societies, Relevant initiatives & projects	Project	>50	N.A.	109

3.2 Stakeholder database

A DIAMAS Stakeholder Database was developed to manage stakeholder knowledge and planning. It contains over 1,100 entries across the nine stakeholder groups. For each target group, the project identified the key organisations, channels of communication, challenges and messages, creating a source of intelligence while liaising with stakeholders over the three years. From here, we also planned our events.

We convened over 4,000 experts across more than 60 DIAMAS-organised (or co-organised) events—including hackathons, webinars, and workshops—delivered in multiple languages and regions. The average number of participants at each event was about 60, although some events were much smaller or much larger. By leveraging existing networks and nurturing new ones, DIAMAS helped catalyse the growth of national and regional Diamond Capacity Centres across Europe.

The period under review began with a shift from data collection to dialogue, with the launch of a well-attended public webinar series on DIAMAS survey results, aligning engagement efforts with other WPs and nominating champions for key stakeholder groups such as funders, IPSPs, and RPOs. Survey-a-thons and DOAS-a-thons followed (see below), which were delivered in many languages for hands-on experiences.

As soon as survey results were in, project partners organised focused webinars in multiple languages both online and offline to open up conversations on our findings and Diamond OA. Those already with strong Diamond networks in place, such as Spain, utilised many opportunities in the project to liaise with their networks through events. Some action initiated the development of new capacity centres in the Nordic region, for example.

The later DIAMAS guidelines and recommendations were co-created with umbrella organisations such as the EUA and Science Europe – leveraging their internal networks – created by and for them. A library conversation series regularly updated and engaged the European library community, where some of the most heated discussions took place. A campaign in 2025 publicised the Registry and Forum. We also organised two online meetings with learned societies, bringing many together for the first time. We also held workshops at conferences, such as at the Munin Conference in November 2024: Introducing DOAS and the Self-assessment Tool and our own events to launch the European Diamond Capacity Hub and the Final Conference.

3.3 Highlighted events

Survey-a-thons

To boost survey participation, we organised over ten online meetings in local languages (from French and Spanish to Italian and Polish) to present the project and answer questions live about the questionnaire as communities filled in the survey. This was also one of the earliest ways to meet and grow the Diamond OA community.

DOAS and DOAS-a-thons

In early 2024, the rollout of key tools in early versions – particularly the Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) and the self-assessment framework – required managing multilingual regional webinars in France, Spain, and the Western Balkans. These sessions served to introduce the tools and to gather feedback that shaped improved versions. A targeted webinar for learned societies led to the launch of a tailored clinic series for that community.

The second half of 2024 saw the introduction of “DOAS-a-thons” – hands-on workshops designed to help institutional publishers adopt the DOAS standard in practice. Pilots in the UK and Ireland helped refine the format, while the library-focused “Conversation Series” expanded, with in-language support in Serbian, Croatian, and Ukrainian to boost participation.

DIAMAS Conversation Series

The *DIAMAS Conversation Series*, jointly organised by EIFL and SPARC Europe, created an informal space for engagement with libraries and other stakeholders, aiming to

share project results, gather feedback, and foster a community around Diamond OA. Five events were organised with an average of 70 participants. The first event presented the DIAMAS landscape report. It focused on the role of libraries in sustaining Diamond OA, financial sustainability challenges, funding mechanisms, and the importance of the workforce and infrastructure. The second session introduced the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) and the associated self-assessment tool to help publishers improve quality and sustainability. The third event presented the EDCH Toolsuite and Guidelines. The fourth session showcased real-world applications of DOAS, featuring experiences from early adopters at the University of Milan, and from Serbia, and the Netherlands.

Across the series, participants discussed how to integrate DIAMAS tools into library services and co-create advocacy and practical resources. The series effectively bridged project outputs with broader community needs. It also positioned libraries as key actors in advancing and supporting Diamond OA practices across Europe. The fifth session focused on the [European Diamond Capacity Hub \(EDCH\) Training Platform](#) – its structure and the training modules designed to support the growth of the Diamond Open Access ecosystem.

DIAMAS Final Conference

A significant dissemination milestone was the DIAMAS Final Conference, held on 3 June in Brussels. The event gathered over 320 registered participants (103 in-person and 219 online), representing a diverse community of stakeholders. A targeted outreach campaign, dedicated graphics, speaker promotion, and post-event follow-up videos, blog posts, and publication of presentations on Zenodo supported the event. The conference also served as a platform to present the WP6 Recommendations publicly, the DOAS self-assessment tool, and the CAP/EDCH infrastructure. These outputs were further disseminated through conference materials, recorded sessions, and follow-up newsletters.

By August 2025, the engagement tracker showed over 6,869 documented stakeholder interactions.

4. Exploitation

To guarantee that DIAMAS' investment effectively benefits the partners and the wider institutional publishing community beyond the end of the project, an exploitation and sustainability strategy was drafted in December 2023 (D7.2 Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement and Exploitation Plan).

4.1 Method

The exploitation strategy of the project was formulated through regular consultation with the project partners and targeted stakeholders: in the first instance, each work package identified specific outputs and exploitable results, which were then confirmed in a DIAMAS KER Overview document. This overview document formed the basis for further discussion on the project's KER and output ownership, exploitation and sustainability among project partners and stakeholders before making concrete decisions on their future exploitation. Stakeholder feedback on the potential relevance of the resources to their respective communities was assessed, and informed exploitation scenarios for the DIAMAS results beyond the project's timeframe were drafted.

4.2 Objectives

In 2024 and 2025, the exploitation plan should serve the twofold objective: providing support to a future network of Diamond Capacity Centres (DCC) and creating the building blocks of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) - a federated infrastructure helping journals align with quality standards and guidelines.

4.3 Implementation during the project

To meet the objectives of the exploitation plan, the following sustainability and exploitation measures were implemented during the project:

- DIAMAS resources (training materials, guidelines, reports) were uploaded in Zenodo, thereby better guaranteeing their access and preservation beyond the life of the project.
- DIAMAS resources were linked to the Common Access Point (CAP) and, eventually, to the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH); thus, they were linked to workflows and tools that IPSPs across Europe are applying and will apply to meet current quality and operational standards.
- DIAMAS resources were made openly available under a CC-BY licence, which allows for their reuse and adaptation (e.g. translation) in the Diamond Capacity Centres managed by project partners.
- The DIAMAS Tools (IPSP registry, self-assessment tool, IPSP forum and toolsuite) were developed as much as possible with open-source software and delivered as open-ended, interoperable components. This approach enables their integration into larger infrastructures and the design of interoperability workflows, allowing the exchange of resources and information across them and for the broader community to build upon them in the years to come.
- Additionally, to enable further exploitation, the Self-Assessment tool was translated into multiple languages and public extension features were added to monitor IPSPs.

The long-term sustainability and further development of the project's tools will be grounded in partners' in-kind contributions, which have already been confirmed by project partners.

5. Maximising and widening impact

DIAMAS deployed activities aimed at widening and maximising impact in the ERA and beyond to ensure the uptake and sustainability of the project's KERs. To achieve this, DIAMAS engaged with national networks and initiatives, associations of university presses and library consortia, and regional and international networks identified in the stakeholder database. Activities were carried out in close coordination with the teams responsible for engagement and for the exploitation of project results. While they shared similar formats and topics with engagement activities, the widening and maximisation activities had a distinct focus: presenting and promoting the project's completed outputs (including deliverables, tools, and services) through online and in-person events, publications, blog posts and practical resources, such as factsheets and checklists that stakeholders could easily understand, translate, and reuse..

At the start of the project, activities, milestones, and deliverables were identified across all work packages that could enhance the impact of the project's outputs both during its lifetime and beyond. This plan was continuously updated and refined throughout the project.

Widening and maximizing activities and resources were developed in close collaboration with the authors of deliverables and resources and team members involved in the development of tools. A shared spreadsheet was created for the project team to record their plans for presenting at conferences. This enabled the coordination team to reach out and offer support with drafting presentation proposals, organizing workshops, or preparing presentation materials.

Factsheets were created and blog posts were published to promote key outputs (e.g. the Diamond Open Access Standard, [IPSP sustainability study](#), [national overviews of institutional publishing](#), and [a guide for developing EDIB strategies](#)) and engage particular stakeholders (e.g. [libraries](#)).

Several outputs were transformed into practical resources. For example, the detailed report on IPSP best practices was adapted into a [Best Practices Checklist for Diamond OA publishers](#), and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) served as the basis for a [brochure](#) for publishers and a [practical guide for journals](#) that can easily be translated

and adapted for local use (e.g. both resources were translated into Serbian and [made available on the Serbian National Open Science Portal](#)).

Conference presentations on specific project outputs aimed to inform stakeholders, showcase their benefits, and promote their reuse. The team also organized in-person and online presentations and workshops for publishers and editors across Southeastern and Eastern Europe, including Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Slovenia and Ukraine. These events enabled the dissemination and uptake of DIAMAS outputs beyond the partner countries and encouraged discussion in multiple languages.

Joint webinars with other Horizon Europe projects such as GraspOS and CRAFT-OA linked discussions on [research assessment](#), infrastructure, and scholarly publishing.

5.1 Exploitation and sustainability of the IPSP Global Network Platform

Throughout the DIAMAS project, all efforts were focused on delivering a range of results. During the project, a dedicated Task (T7.5) worked on the DIAMAS project exploitation and sustainability of the IPSP Global Network. This included creating a thriving Diamond Open Access community that would last beyond the project's lifetime and be a stepping stone for further global development and scalability. To facilitate this transition, the DIAMAS online Common Access Point was developed together with focused efforts to motivate the community to transfer from DIAMAS to EDCH.

5.1.1 European Diamond Capacity Hub

The development of the Common Access Point (CAP) website under WP4, led by LIBER, was at the core of securing DIAMAS results. During the DIAMAS project, the CAP was transformed into the entry point of the European Diamond Capacity Hub, aiming to support the IPSP Global Network Platform.

At the end of the DIAMAS project LIBER, as contractor of the CAP, will transfer all rights, titles and interests to OPERAS, the EDCH fiscal host, and this will be recorded in an Intellectual Property Assignment Agreement. The EDCH has already secured the rights for further infrastructure development in the future.

The European Diamond Capacity Hub now includes all major DIAMAS resources, such as engagement resources, including the stakeholder database (with GDPR compliance taken into account), DOAS-a-thon guides, and webinar recordings. This ensures the sustainability of the DIAMAS community beyond the project's end.

5.1.2 Moving the community from DIAMAS to the EDCH

Now that the DIAMAS project is coming to its end, the community and network that have been built will have to transfer to the new infrastructure for Diamond Open Access: the European Diamond Capacity Hub, including the Registry and Forum. The EDCH was designed well before the end of the project to enable a smooth transition. As soon as the EDCH was launched in January 2025, communication focused on inviting the community to sign up for the Forum and EDCH social media channels, as well as stakeholders for the Registry. By early August, 174 individuals had already signed up for the Forum, and 138 stakeholders for the Registry. To be as inclusive as possible, a translation tool was included in the Forum to offer community members the opportunity to communicate in their preferred language.

Much effort was devoted to targeting specific regions in Europe with information about the EDCH after observing certain regions lagging behind in registering for the Forum or Registry.

5.1.3 Exploitation and sustainability plan beyond the DIAMAS project

At the end of the DIAMAS project an exploitation and sustainability plan was drafted to ensure the future exploitation and sustainability of the DIAMAS project results (see Annex I). The DIAMAS Exploitation and Sustainability Plan builds on the communication, dissemination and engagement strategies carried out during the project. It secures future exploitation and sustainability of the project results and focuses on:

- a) developing an exploitation strategy beyond the project's lifetime,
- b) identifying the requirements, strategies and tools for fostering and developing the IPSP Global Network, building on its existing and growing network of organisations and communities
- c) providing a sustainability plan for the hosting platform of the IPSP Global Network.

During the third General Assembly in Brussels on 2 June 2025, the ownership of the intellectual property of the DIAMAS project's key exploitable results (KER) was secured by all partners. Additionally, it was agreed that each partner will become a member of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), to better ensure the viability of the DIAMAS KER within the EDCH community.

6. Next Steps

This document has summarised what has been done for the Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation efforts of the DIAMAS project, led by WP7, based on the plan as described in D7.2. Each section has sought to describe the results achieved and how they have established the DIAMAS brand, shared project updates and results, recruited and engaged stakeholders, widened and maximised the impact of the project in and beyond the ERA, and the eventual uptake of the project's results.

During the project, two milestones enabled us to review and monitor the success of essential parts of this strategy – Requirements and strategy for Widening Impact (M12) and Website Communications Kit and Social Media Iteration 1 (M18). In addition, the project review at month 15 allowed us to fine-tune and adjust the strategies depending on the success of specific actions and wider developments of DIAMAS. This created a flexible approach and enabled us to respond to the progress of the project and the needs of key stakeholders.

At the end of the project, we look forward to the future uptake of the legacy of the DIAMAS project by laying the groundwork through consistent community engagement and by building the new, longer-term home for DIAMAS, the EDCH, well ahead of time. The further evolution of DIAMAS results had already begun during the project when the Common Access Point evolved into the European Diamond Capacity Hub. In 2025, we took the opportunity to scale DIAMAS outputs globally in the ALMASI project, with both projects sharing the same lead organisation. The vast community of practice that has been formed and facilitated by the EDCH Registry and Forum provides a steady foundation for further uptake of DIAMAS outputs.

ANNEX I

Exploitation and Sustainability plan

The DIAMAS project ends in August 2025; however the results of the project will be sustained and further exploited beyond the project end. To secure the exploitation and sustainability of the project results an Exploitation and Sustainability plan was prepared.

The Exploitation and Sustainability plan set out below describes the exploitation of the project results and focuses on:

1. Key Project Results to Sustain and Exploit
2. The Development of European Diamond Capacity Hub
3. Ownership and IPR Management
4. Exploitation of KER's
5. Financial Sustainability
6. Target users
7. Capacity Building and Skills Retention
8. Replication and Scalability
9. Policy Alignment and Societal Uptake
10. Governance and Monitoring
11. Risk Analysis and Mitigation

1. Key exploitable results to sustain and exploit

In this first section, an overview is provided of the exploitable results produced during the DIAMAS project that need to be secured for future use and uptake.

The project aimed to produce multiple exploitable results that enhanced our understanding of the current state of institutional scientific publishing in Europe. This included better coordination among institutional publishing services and initiatives at the non-technical level, improved overall service efficiency – especially in multilingual environments – and the provision of actionable recommendations for strategies regarding institutional publishing in research-performing organisations throughout the European Research Area.

The table below lists the Key Exploitable Results, including the exploitation and sustainability strategies completed during the project, which will support its exploitation and sustainability after the project has ended.

KERs as stated in project proposal

Key Exploitable Results	Target Stakeholder	Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy
Landscape mapping & gap analysis	All stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement throughout project and consortium comms channels - Early release of data under CCO - Dissemination and preservation on Zenodo under CCO - Continuous communication through global network platform
DOAS (formerly known as EQSIP)	IPSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through project events (webinars and workshops) - Dissemination and preservation on Zenodo under CCO - Continuous communication through Global Network platform - Regular Updates with engagement via Global Network forum
Global Network, including EDCH, (formerly known as Common Access Point (CAP), toolsuite, training materials, guidelines and forum	IPSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination through project and consortium communication channels - Integration in OPERAS catalogue of services for continuous communication and support
ED&I Tools	IPSP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through events (webinars and workshop) - Engagement and dissemination through project and consortium communication channels - Outreach via T7.4 - Integration in the global network platform supported by OPERAS - Outreach via the international advisory board
Quality and sustainability self-assessment tools	IPSP and institutions' financial departures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through project events (webinars and workshop) - Continuous communication through Global Network platform - Technical sustainability of the Self Assessment Tools ensured by FECYT
Actionable recommendations	RFOs, RPOs, policy-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement through project events (webinars and workshop) - Continuous communication through Global Network platform - Continuous advocacy and updates by specialised umbrella organisations: EUA (RPOs), Science Europe (RFO), OPERAS (national policy-making bodies)
All KERs	All stakeholders	ALL KERs will be integrated in the 'Institutional Publishing Global Network' that will become one of the core services of OPERAS

2. The Development of the European Diamond Capacity Hub

During the project the development of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH - <https://DIAMAS.org/>) took place building on the results of the DIAMAS project. The EDCH has been designed as a federated infrastructure to support the quality and sustainability of Diamond OA publishing across Europe. It responds to the diverse

needs of the Diamond OA community through integrated services and a participatory governance model that fosters community involvement.

The EDCH offers six core services ([Arasteh et al. 2025](#)) to Publishers, Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSP), and Institutional Publishing Technology Providers (IPTP). The EDCH Registry and Forum ([Angoloni et al. 2025](#)) specifically aim to support the sustainability and growth of the IPSP/IPTP network that the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects have established ([Paulhac et al. 2025](#)). They serve as spaces for mapping organisations involved in Diamond OA publishing and fostering collaboration among community members: the Registry showcases the organisation's services and capacities, and the Forum is an online venue for dialogue, knowledge exchange, and coordination of activities.

In alignment with the identified services, the operational activities of the EDCH are coordinated by six Task Forces (<https://DIAMAS.org/task-forces>) focusing on community-building, transitioning to Diamond OA, fundraising, quality alignment, skills development, and tools development. The Task Forces work collaboratively to ensure the services evolve and remain relevant to community needs, represented by IPSPs, IPTPs, and Capacity Centres.

The EDCH's communication and engagement strategy highlights its scope of serving as both a federated infrastructure and a collective that supports the community of practice around Diamond OA. To this end, a network of National Capacity Centres (NCC) was launched in June 2025, with the aim of fostering cross-regional collaboration as well as support the uptake of the EDCH services in the respective countries and regions. NCCs will have a critical role in adapting resources to local languages, aligning with regional policies, and embedding Diamond OA practices.

3. Ownership and IPR Management

Ownership and IP rights of the DIAMAS results have been secured to guarantee the long-term sustainability and further development of the project's tools.

Ownership

The DIAMAS Consortium held its third General Assembly in Brussels on 2 June 2025. During this meeting, the 23 partners voted on the ownership of the intellectual property of the DIAMAS project's key exploitable results (KER). The partners overwhelmingly decided that the ownership of the DIAMAS KER will remain with the consortium members. Additionally, it was agreed that each partner will become a member of the

European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) in the future. This membership will ensure the viability of the DIAMAS KER within the EDCH community.

IP Rights Common Access Point/EDCH

In August 2025, subcontractor Pontemedia concluded its work on the CAP and delivered the final result, including a final report. The report was reviewed and accepted by members of the DIAMAS consortium WP4. On the finalisation of this task, and according to the contract between LIBER as Contractor and Pontemedia, all rights, titles and interests were transferred to LIBER. By the end of the DIAMAS project, LIBER will transfer all rights, titles and interests to OPERAS, which will be recorded in an Intellectual Property Assignment Agreement. Thus, the EDCH (CAP) has secured the rights for further infrastructure development in the future.

4. Exploitation of KER's

This section describes the plans for non-commercial exploitation beyond the lifetime of the DIAMAS project. The role of partners and stakeholders in the exploitation of the KER's are further elaborated on.

Non-commercial exploitation of DIAMAS results

The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) will be responsible for exploiting the results of DIAMAS, functioning as a collaborative and distributed infrastructure. A distinction is made between documents and live services within the Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

While there are no immediate plans to update the landscape report or actionable recommendations, these documents will remain accessible and highlighted as crucial resources for various stakeholders on the EDCH website. This will ensure their continued access and exploitation beyond the project's conclusion.

Tools and services, including DOAS and its Self-assessment platform, the Tool suite, and DEI tools, will be updated via EDCH participation in future funded projects. Their exploitation will also continue within the EDCH framework.

Access to these services is free, but may be limited to stakeholders within the European Research Area or even EDCH members, especially for "two sided" platforms like the Registry, Toolsuite, Training platform, and forum. For these platforms, a distinction is made between "read mode" (accessing information) and "write mode" (adding information).

The types of access corresponding to different project results are summarised in the table below.

Result	Read access	Write access
Landscape mapping	all	n.a
Recommendations	all	n.a
DOAS	all	n.a
Self-assessment tools	all	all
Toolsuite and guidelines	all	EDCH members
Registry	all	ERA organisations
Forum	all	Members of ERA organisations
ED&I tools	all	EDCH members
Common Access Point	all	EDCH coordination team

Role of partners and stakeholders in exploitation.

All project materials are covered by the CC-BY 4.0 open license, allowing partners and stakeholders to freely use and adapt them. This includes translating content and integrating it into local resources to meet specific audience needs.

Certain project partners operate the tools and services that all partners can exploit without prior consent. The EDCH collectively exploits these resources as a pan-European infrastructure. Its aim is to provide tools and services to all stakeholders in the European Research Area (ERA), especially capacity centres that support Diamond Open Access publishing at institutional, disciplinary, or national levels.

5. Financial Sustainability

The long-term financial viability of the EDCH and its key exploitable results is intrinsically linked to its robust financial model. This model is designed to integrate a diverse array of funding streams, including one-off grants, recurring annual membership fees, and valuable in-kind contributions from partner organisations.

Presently, the EDCH's operational foundation is bolstered by initial grants from prominent funding bodies such as the Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR), the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF). Furthermore, critical in-kind contributions are generously provided

by DIAMAS partners, who have committed to operating various EDCH services without charge.

A strategic shift is planned at the start of 2026, aiming to establish a more stable and predictable support collection mechanism rooted in membership contributions. This new framework will differentiate between two distinct categories of members:

- **Supporting Members:** These members will provide direct financial contributions, thereby offering vital monetary support to the EDCH's core team and services. The fee structure for supporting members will be carefully calibrated to reflect their financial capacity, taking into account several key parameters such as organisational size, budget, and the GDP of their respective countries. The implementation of this financial contribution model for supporting members is slated for the end of 2025.
- **Operational Members:** These members contribute in-kind support by actively operating the EDCH's diverse services. Currently, operational members are engaged in the process of evaluating the monetary value of the support they provide through their free operational services. The current operational members and the services they manage are:
 - Registry and Forum: OPERAS
 - DOAS and Self-Assessment Platform: FECYT
 - Training Platform: Aix-Marseille Université (AMU)/OpenEdition
 - Toolsuite and Guidelines: To be determined
 - ED&I Tools: TSV

As we mentioned in our second policy brief, as the EDCH serves the needs of the whole ERA, we also think there should be more structural support from the European Commission provided in the next funding round through a Grant to Identified Beneficiary scheme.

Finally, the EDCH is fiscally hosted by OPERAS which is expected to become an ERIC by the end of 2027.

6. Target users

During the DIAMAS project an active and engaged community was developed. This section describes how the different stakeholder groups will continue to be engaged with follow-up initiatives of the DIAMAS project, building on the DIAMAS project results.

Nine stakeholder groups

The project identified nine stakeholder groups: funders, IPSPs, learned societies, libraries, Diamond Open Access Action Plan signatories, policymakers, RPOs, research assessment agencies, as well as researchers, teachers and students. Each stakeholder

group was deemed likely to be interested in the project results and to have vital feedback and input to shape the project's work. They were also seen as the principal adopters of the proposed change and service consumers of the project.

Task forces to foster engagement

The project established task forces to support dissemination and engagement activities and to convene and collaborate online, targeting specific stakeholders. DIAMAS worked closely with all stakeholders during the project, bringing together over 4,000 experts across Europe to project engagement activities.

Post project engagement

After the project, key project partners will continue to liaise with the primary stakeholder audiences. Since all key project partners are umbrella organisations, they will reach many hundreds of organisations.

The table below gives an overview of the stakeholder audiences and the key partners who will exploit DIAMAS outputs and liaise after the project.

STAKEHOLDER	PARTNER
Funders	Science Europe
IPSPs	EUA
Learned societies	TSV
Libraries	SPARC Europe, LIBER, EIFL
OA Diamond Action Plan signatories	Science Europe
Policymakers	SPARC Europe and Science Europe
RPOs	EUA and Science Europe

Key partners will use existing channels such as events, internal expert meetings, working groups, social media and other opportunities to engage with the communities on the EDCH and DIAMAS content as the EDCH gains ground.

The EDCH [Registry](#) and [Forum](#), dedicated virtual spaces for fostering collaboration and networking among the Diamond Open Access community members, lie in the core of the Diamond OA Community.

7. Capacity Building and Skills Retention

This section describes how skills, know-how, and expertise will be preserved or transferred in the future for training programmes, open educational resources and support for researchers and professionals.

Training programmes

The training programmes are implemented, maintained and updated on the Moodle-based EDCH training platform, for which AMU (OpenEdition) retains full ownership. The platform installation and the data it contains will be transferred to AMU for migration to a different hosting environment, which will either be hosted by a third-party or self-hosted.

Individual courses that make up training programmes can be exported in a compressed archive containing all course data, activities, resources, user data, if selected, etc., for reuse or upload in similar Moodle environments.

Open educational resources

All educational resources (training materials) hosted on the Training platform are made available for download on Zenodo, under a CC BY licence, which facilitates reuse.

Each course's expository training materials (e.g. infographics) are made available for download on the EDCH Training platform..

Support for researchers and professionals

An FAQ page and a support contact email aid training platform users, such as researchers and professionals, when using the platform and its training materials. Users are also invited to send requests to participate in the platform's evolution with different roles: training and course development, review, delivery, or subject-matter expertise sharing.

Future developments include offering onboarding toolkits for trainers who use the platform to adapt content into a pedagogical form and upskilling sessions in instructional design and training delivery.

8. Replication and Scalability

This section describes the replication and scalability of the DIAMAS results at the global level.

ALMASI project

Already during its lifetime, the DIAMAS project has been scaled to other global regions via the ALMASI project *Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit OA Publishing Services Internationally (2025-2028)*, which was awarded in the context of the call 'HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-ERA-01-08 – Global cooperation in not-for-profit OA

publishing’. The project involves 16 partners from three continents: Africa, Europe and Latin America. DIAMAS and ALMASI share the same scientific coordinator, OPERAS.

The ALMASI project will work towards gaining a better understanding of the current landscape of non-profit OA publishing in the three regions. It aims to co-design and align measures on quality standards, training resources, as well as institutional and national policy development to ensure the sustainability of non-profit OA publishing.

The project aims to compare the tools, services, guidelines, and best practices developed in the DIAMAS project with those developed in Africa and Latin America with a view to co-creative alignment, discovery, and understanding.

DIAMAS outputs and lessons learnt will be leveraged effectively within ALMASI since both projects share common experts.

Global non-profit publishing ecosystem

An aligned non-profit publishing ecosystem will take into account specific needs across the diversity of disciplines, geographical regions, and languages. It will focus on the harmonisation and consolidation of existing non-profit publishing services and solutions, and will establish a common framework for knowledge transfer, coordination, and strategic alignment.

The ALMASI project can be seen as a pilot contributing to a Global Diamond Alliance.

9. Policy Alignment and Societal Uptake

DIAMAS aimed to reinforce the role of Diamond OA as a central pillar of open science, to develop a more equitable, inclusive, and resilient scholarly publishing ecosystem. By launching the EDCH, the project has laid the groundwork for sustainable infrastructure that supports the coordination and capacity building of Diamond OA across Europe.

To ensure the longevity and broader impact of its outcomes, DIAMAS has delivered comprehensive policy recommendations (D6.2) addressing funders, institutional leaders, and policymakers. These will be further advanced in the ALMASI project, which will explore national and international OA policy frameworks and funding models – particularly in Africa, Europe, and Latin America. By creating a non-profit policy and funder forum, ALMASI will build on DIAMAS’ groundwork to support global, sustainable Diamond OA publishing, identifying best practices and fostering cross-regional learning.

Societal uptake of DIAMAS outputs will be driven by active engagement with stakeholders in academia, non-profit publishers, and policy communities. The project’s focus on Diamond OA as the most equitable model of scholarly communication will help

enhance public trust and foster meaningful participation in science and research. Continued collaboration through initiatives like the EDCH and NCCs ensures that these values are embedded into the infrastructure and practices of scholarly communication systems.

DIAMAS outputs promote the resilience of the scholarly communication ecosystem by ensuring it is accessible, trustworthy, and shaped by the public interest rather than profit. DIAMAS thereby strengthens the operational foundation of non-commercial publishing and fosters long-term engagement between institutions, policymakers, and communities. This collaborative model ensures that research dissemination remains a public good, responsive to diverse regional needs and aligned with the principles of openness, inclusivity, and social justice.

10. Governance and Monitoring

The EDCH was officially launched in January 2025, with its governing bodies fully established. Its governance structure is intentionally lightweight, designed primarily to ensure diverse community representation in decision-making processes.

There are three levels of governance:

- The **Assembly** consists of Community Members: representatives of Diamond Capacity Centres, Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools & Technology Providers that join the European Diamond Capacity Hub. Community Members can participate in various Task Forces.
- The **Steering Committee** is composed of public and not-for-profit organisations (e.g. charities, foundations, associations, RFOs, RPOs) that financially contribute to the European Diamond Capacity Hub.
- The **Executive Committee** oversees its daily operations. National and international organisations involved in various aspects of Diamond OA publishing – are part of this committee and contribute in kind by leading key EDCH task forces and services

The Assembly, the Steering Committee, the Executive Committee, and Task Forces are supported by the EDCH Coordination Team.

EDCH services integrate tools and services from the DIAMAS and Craft-OA projects. Operational members lead thematic task forces, which meet regularly to oversee service operations, identify requirements, and plan for future developments.

Here is the list of task forces with their services:

Task Force	Services	Lead
Community	Registry, Forum	OPERAS, EIFL
Quality alignment	DOAS, Self-assessment platform	FECYT, DOAJ
Skills and Competences	Toolsuite, Guidelines, Training platform	AMU, JISC
Tools and Technologies	Craft-OA KERs	OPERAS, DOAJ
Diamondisation	-	OPERAS
Funding	-	ANR, SPARC Europe, OPERAS

The EDCH tools and services are actively monitored using a third-party service that provides real-time updates on their availability and operational status. The monitoring probes run globally from multiple locations, and verify that the EDCH services are available and respond without any time-out or error. This service collects and reports historical availability data, and computes an availability indicator.

The EDCH status page is publicly accessible at <https://status.DIAMAS.org>, all EDCH stakeholders can view the current status of the EDCH services, and review their history.

The EDCH monitoring service sends notifications via multiple channels, instantly informing the coordination team about any change in service status, allowing to react quickly. The constant monitoring helps identify intermittent errors that may otherwise have been unnoticed, allowing to proactively investigate and address them. Anyone can subscribe to announcements and receive notifications by email, rather than having to manually consult the status page.

When an unplanned downtime is reported and confirmed, the relevant service providers are contacted to investigate and resolve the incident. During the incident resolution, the EDCH team uses the status page to keep users informed. It is also used to announce scheduled downtime.

11. Risk analysis and mitigation

Low interest in further uptake of the DIAMAS results

A significant challenge for projects, especially those with non-technical outputs, is ensuring the continued uptake of their results post-completion. This is often due to a disruption in branding, as outputs are typically tied to the project's name, which becomes irrelevant once the project concludes.

To mitigate this, DIAMAS proactively integrated its results into the EDCH before project completion, ensuring genuine exploitation rather than a post-factum handover. Upon project completion, these results were fully rebranded under the EDCH's banner. Dissemination, communication, and engagement activities are now supported by a full-time community manager, and will soon be joined by a communication officer. By the end of the project, the EDCH had been operational for six months and was fostering a vibrant community of users of the project's outputs.

Loss of engagement in the community of practice

Two potential factors contribute to this risk: competition from other service providers and the typical linguistic barrier across Europe, which hinders engagement with English content and interactions.

Currently, there is no competitor at the European Research Area (ERA) level. Numerous initiatives exist to create and develop national, disciplinary, and institutional capacity centres in various contexts. These initiatives are not competitors; they are complementary to the EDCH. They operate at different levels, and the EDCH's aim is to provide them with resources to support their own communities. EDCH is actively establishing a network of National Capacity Centres to strengthen relations between the EDCH and diverse local communities throughout the ERA.

To overcome the linguistic barrier, various strategies are employed. These include translating interfaces and content across EDCH platforms, encouraging users to communicate in their native languages while utilising automatic translation into English, and implementing other supportive measures. Structurally, the distributed nature of OPERAS, the EDCH fiscal host, is leveraged to foster engagement with national communities. OPERAS national nodes play a crucial role in facilitating translation and organising local events.

Unsuccessful transfer of followers from DIAMAS to EDCH communication channels

Communication efforts for the project began in early 2025, laying the groundwork for broader dissemination and engagement. This initial phase focused on establishing core messages and identifying key stakeholders. As the project nears its conclusion in August 2025, communication activities are significantly intensified. This increased effort aims to maximise the dissemination of project results and ensure a lasting impact.

Instead of being deleted, the DIAMAS website is archived via the Internet Archive. This strategic decision ensures the continued availability of project information and resources. A clear reference to the new web environment is included on the archived DIAMAS website, guiding users to updated content and platforms. Additionally, a direct link to the archived DIAMAS website is integrated into the EDCH website, facilitating seamless access and cross-referencing for relevant audiences.

GDPR

The project contacted stakeholders and used their data for the project's internal stakeholder database. During project events, attendees were asked if they wanted more information about the project and asked for explicit permission to communicate with them further. All these interactions concerning personal data, were governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The project-wide Privacy Statement (available on the DIAMAS website: [link](#)) was used as a reference during outreach work. The data controller (appointed from WP1 – Management and Coordination of the Project) acted as the contact point for stakeholders who wished to contact the project with privacy queries.

Now that the DIAMAS project is coming to an end, the community and network that has been built will transition to the new environment: the European Diamond Capacity Hub, including the Registry and Forum. Under the GDPR regulations, the privacy-sensitive information in the stakeholder databases and contact lists cannot be transferred from DIAMAS to the EDCH. To mitigate the risk of some stakeholders and community members not moving from the DIAMAS environment to the EDCH, communication focuses on encouraging the community to sign up for the Forum and EDCH social media channels, and the Registry.

Low flexibility to deviate from the Grant Agreement

During the project, the strategic decision was taken to evolve DIAMAS outputs towards the European Diamond Capacity Hub. This strategy involved rebranding project outputs and thus a potential formal deviation from the Grant Agreement.

For future projects, it would be beneficial to allow flexibility to prioritise well-argued deviations from initial strategies over strict adherence to formal checks.

